

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

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Abstract

This research is basically an analytical study of a Baloch tribe Sakhani which had played an important role in the history. Although this tribe is mostly inhabited in Punjab but also found in other provinces of Pakistan in the past and even now in KPK and Sindh to Balochistan. Sakhani tribe is considered a powerful tribe of the past and their history is also recognized against the rebellion of Sewstan during the time of Aurangzeb Alamgir. The bravery of the nation in history is undeniable. Whether it is the battle of Sewstan or the war against the Sikhs. Whether it is a clash from Nawab Bahawalpur or reaching Nawab Muzaffar Khan with bare swords during the siege of Multan is his national service. Similarly, a huge vote bank of Sikhs in Dera Ghazi Khan is their political power which they have been using locally for the last two or three decades to win district council seats or several union council chairs. His vote bank is very important in the National and Provincial Assembly elections in Dera Ghazi Khan. The paper highlights the role of Sakhani tribe in the politics of Dera Ghazi Khan.

Keywords; Baloch, Sakhani, Rind, Tribe, Dera Ghazi Khan, Domki etc.

Introduction

The history of the Baloch nation is centuries old when they settled near Caspian then from there to Syria and Aleppo, from Iran via Kerman to Makran and Balochistan. Most of the Baloch tribes are descended from Mir Jalal Khan's sons Rind, Lashar, Hot, Korai and Jato. In Jang-e-Nali, the rivalry between the Baloch leaders Chakar Azam and Mir Lashar and their desire for political supremacy weakened the Baloches by entangling them in war and Chakar Azam turned to Punjab. Baloch tribes settled in different parts of Punjab from Derajat and

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

then from Multan and many Baloch tribes settled here and reached from Derajat to Sahiwal. - Derajat was ruled by Mirani Baloch for a long time while the Hout tribe of Baloch ruled Dera Ismail Khan in the northern part of Derajat.¹ Sheikh Sadiq Ali in his book mentioned many Baloch tribes who are settled in areas of Sindh and Balochistan and Sakhani tribe is one of them.² Muhammad Sardar Khan, while talking about many Baloch races, also mentioned the numerous Baloch tribes, the number of which he mentions in thousands. Azam Suhdari has also mentioned several Baloch tribes in his book. While Abdul Qadir Leghari and Ehsan Changwani have also described the Baloch Sakhani tribe as a major tribe of the past. One of the most important and powerful Baloch tribes is the Sakhani tribe, which is an important tribe in the past. It is spread over Dera Division. This research paper mainly covers the history of the Baloch Sakhani tribe and this tribe is currently settled in the plains with ethnic Baloch status. This tribe is a war tribe belonging to Rind branch of Baloches which was a powerful tribe in the past whose innumerable examples of bravery are well known. This tribe with different names from Ishaq Ani is today inhabited in large numbers in Punjab, Sindh, Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.³ The Sukhani tribe is going through various ups and downs of history and today it is known by its name. Its vote bank plays a crucial role. This research paper examines the ancient civilization, history and culture of the Sukhani tribe, the ancient Balochi epic temperament as well as the political and social power and political role of the tribe in the current political and electoral system.

Research Methodology

If the subject is taken into consideration, it is clear that this research paper with historical background has been completed with the help of historical material in which primary and secondary sources containing documentary material have been used as historical evidence of this paper completed by going through critical stages. Therefore, adopting historical method of research, values style is an important aspect of this article. In addition to the primary and secondary sources, some information is part of the Chest Gazette which has been obtained through interviews with various elders.

Literature Review

For this topic of historical nature, the historical material has also been studied to supplement this theme. It includes ancient Balochi poetry as well as Muslim races of Sindh and Balochistan, castes of Punjab, history of Baloches, peoples living in the homeland, history of Dera Ghazi Khan, history of Dera Ghazi Khan, Tahfatul-kram, election results, Baloch in the mirror of history, Baloch Dera Ghazi Khan, Gul Bihar, Urban Union Council No. 11, Articles, Newspapers and Interviews.

Importance of Topic

This topic is unique in that it is the first research paper to be written on the Sukhani (Ishaqani) tribe and no work has been done on this topic before. Dera Ghazi Khan has been working only on the tribes with the status of Tamandar. However, no action was taken against the non-Tamandar tribes. While the Sukhani tribe has a significant influence in the entire Dera division, it also has a bright past historically and politically. Whether it was the siege of Multan or the invasion of Ranjit Singh and Nawab Bahawalpur, this tribe rendered significant

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

services to the region. Political, social and very important historical status is its bright chapter.

Discussion

In addition to discussing the subject, it is important to first explain the main character of the subject, the word Sakhani, how and where it originated. Because one of the interesting things about the evolution of the word Sukhani is that the Sikhs are the descendants of Sikhs. Sukha Khan is a descendant of Baloch or Nutkani like this. Some people think that they are Jats and according to some they are Chandia. Some say that if they are Baloch then why they speak Saraiki. How were they powerful in ancient times? How did their power end? Why don't they have desire? We discuss the answers to such questions in this article.

Apart from the Sakhani, most of the Baloch tribes living in the plains speak Saraiki because of their society. Only a few percent speak Balochi. Similarly, the Baloch up to the tribal area have now adopted Saraiki language instead of Balochi. Saraiki has now gained the status of cultural and economic language in the region. Due to this, the Baloches in the region have remained Baloch to an ethnic extent and this aspect of language change is the reason why Baloch teachers speak Saraiki. So it is not surprising that Baloch teachers have shifted from Baloch to Saraiki. Not only Dera Ghazi Khan but the whole area was invaded by Sikhs in the 19th century, so it is a joke to say that the Sikh nation is from Sikhs. Then due to mutual kinship different nations and tribes are present in the same society and similar Sukhani and Chandia tribes also live together and in Sindh these Sukhani became known as Sakhani Chandio. In the area of Mazaris are called Sakhani Mazaris although there are two different tribes. Similarly, unlike the past, why they are weak today, it is not a ridiculous thing. The rise and fall of nations is a part of history. And the answer to Tamandari is that during the British rule in 1867, the tribes which were armed in the western hilly part of Dera Ghazi Khan got Tamandari.⁴

The arrival of Baloch tribes in Punjab started after the battle of Nali when the 30 year war between Rind and Lashar ended with the victory of Rind and defeat of Lasharis. After this battle Mir Rind Chakar Azam turned towards Punjab The fighting between the Balochs weakened them and their various tribes dispersed and settled in Sindh and Punjab. It should be noted that the strength and bravery of the Baloch was exemplary and their leader, despite being many times more powerful than the Mongols, was found to be a compassionate, God-fearing, compassionate enemy, guardian of women's honor and dignity. In order to put an end to mutual rivalries and grievances, he said goodbye to his homeland along with his people and tribes and turned from Sibi to Sanghar and then to Punjab. After his arrival in Punjab, he never bargained with the rulers of Delhi and other rulers, but proved himself the protector and leader of the nation. Chakar Azam Khan Azam as a hero helped Emperor Humayun in 1555 and finally died in 1556. Khan Azam's death deprived the Baloch of central leadership and dispersed their territorial and geographical power. The Balochs started settling in Sindh and Punjab, including Balochistan. Thus the Balochs were divided into hundreds of small and large tribes. Muhammad Sardar Khan Baloch in his book *Baloch Generations* mentions one lakh Baloch families.⁵ If we talk about the Baloches of Derajat, it is clear that there were many large tribes here. One of the most important of these tribes was the Ishaqani tribe, the descendants of Mir Ishaq. About Mir Ishaq Historians believe that the lineage of Mir Ishaq in

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

the 14th generation back to Baba Amir Hamza, the ancestor of the Baloches, while in the 7th line it goes back to Mir Jalal Khan. Ancient Balochi poetry shows that Mir Rind Mir Jalal Khan's son Ishaqani is the ancestor of the nation. Mir Ishaq II is called Mir Ali Nautak, brother of Mir Bahadur and Mir Ahmad Khan, son of Mir Muhammad and grandson of Mir Hassan Khan. The descendants of Ishaq Khan, Ishaqani, Sahaqani, Sakhani, Sahkani, Sahkani, and Sakhani under different names, have gone through the ups and downs of history and settled all over the subcontinent.⁶

The author has found out through research that there are many people of the Sikh nation living in different parts of India. Similarly, there is a settlement near Dhaka in Bangladesh. Apart from Sindh, Balochistan and Punjab in Pakistan, this nation is also inhabited in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Regarding the Sukhani tribe, according to Mir Chakar Khan Tamandar Domki, who has a record of the history of the Baloch nation, says that the Sukhani is a large Baloch tribe, even the Sabagani people who are around the Rojhan Mazari. The Sakhani are an influential tribe of Dera Ghazi Khan.⁷

At the beginning of the seventeenth century, it was a very powerful tribe and its influence was spread all over the region, thanks to which they got jagirs in different places. During the Mughal period, when Prince Moazzam became the ruler of Multan, in order to put an end to the revolt in the western direction, Moazzam sent Nawab Ghulam Muhammad Khan Sukhani to deal with the revolt of Siwastan after several failures. So the Nawab's army not only succeeded but also established peace and order in the area. In response, the Nawab was later made governor of Sewastan. And he remained governor until 1702, which increased the power of the tribe. Similarly, in the eighteenth century, the Sukhani tribe strongly resisted the Western invaders who invaded Afghanistan.

The Miranis supported the Miranis during the Durrani invasion, but the Kalhoras invaded the south and suddenly attacked the Sukhani tribe near Fazilpur, causing severe damage. Similarly, during the reign of Ranjit Singh, the Sikhs put up strong resistance at Rajanpur, Sakhaniwala and Basti Fauja. Their power was shattered. It is clear that the Sukhani tribe put up strong resistance in the plains. Similarly, in the siege of Multan, in support of Nawab Muzaffar Khan Shaheed, members of Sukhani tribe arrived with naked swords and many people were martyred, some of whose graves are in Mouza Bait Kapahi district of Muzaffargarh, which is an example of their bravery.⁸

The tribe then dispersed in the plains and most of the properties were confiscated. Even in the English period, this tribe did not get any acceptance. However, Ghulam Haider Khan Sukhani held a high position like Survey of India. A teacher from Dera Ghazi Khan also attended the 20th Century Anjman-e-Islamia and the Muslim Education Conference and contributed. Hutto Ram, on the history of Balochistan, p. He said the number of unarmed people was 600. But at the same time the precedent of the Sukhani nation has also been written to Jahan Khan and the Sukhani has been described as a large tribe and the number of disarmed persons has been stated as 1250.⁹ Historians speculate that Hutto Ram, who is also the author of Gul Bihar, has a different opinion. Thus in another place he described the Sikhs as a branch of Dareshk and said that they were descendants of Shah.¹⁰ Hukam Chand, referring to the large tribes of different Baloches, has written the word Sukhani as Sakhani and has termed it as a branch of Randad Baloch. 11 The book also details the genealogy of Baloch in which the name of the ancestor of the Sikh nation is Ishaq Khan but due to lack of

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

knowledge there is a problem of identity. There are more than one person named Ishaq and now there is a difference between them is not possible.¹² While in the same book, on page 66, it is stated that there is a place called Sakhaniwala. Later, Bazdars came and settled here. But Hukam Chand did not elaborate.¹³

Some elders of the nation say that the Sikhs migrated from here when Dera Ghazi Khan was invaded from Sindh in the south. The second tradition is that the army of Nawab of Bahawalpur came. Which is not correct History in Rajanpur is said to have originated from Sukhani Ishaqani. According to this, there are dozens of families of Sukhani Baloches living in Rajanpur. I have moved. Apart from Rajanpur city, Pur district especially Jampur, Fazilpur, Rojhan are also inhabited by Sikhs. They are now almost an ethnic Baloch and speak mostly Sikh Saraiki instead of their mother tongue Balochi.¹⁴ According to Huttu Ram, some other tribes are also living near Mangarotha and these Tamandars are part of Nutkani. Among them, the Sukhani Baloch who live in Mouza Tub are different from the Natkani people.¹⁵ Noor Mohammad Thind believes that Sakhaniwala which is present in Layyah district is due to the same tribe. I belong to a Baloch tribe and according to him it is a branch of Natkani Baloch. One of the descendants of Mir Aali was named Ishaq Khan and from whom this tribe came into existence. In Urdu, these Ishaqani, then Sahakani and now Sukhani are found in Layyah district. Most of them are found within the division. The famous areas of their residence are Kotaddu and Layyah. There is a large number of this nation here.¹⁶ According to some, the Sargani tribe is also to be taught, mainly moving to different areas. They are also settled in different parts of Dera Division, especially inside Layyah.¹⁷ The Sakhani are basically the Rind Baloch tribe. It was first the Ishaq tribe but then its name gradually changed to Sukhani. It is mostly inhabited in Ghazi Khan Division. Sakhani also moved to this area after a year of war and then settled in Dera Ghazi Khan. Thousands of them are present in Ghazi Khan division. They are very important in the constituencies. The vote bank of their community plays a key role in causing victory and defeat.¹⁸ Ehsan thinks that Sukhani Baloch is Rind and he is a descendant of Sukhani Khan but this is not true. Dera Ghazi Khan District is also inhabited in large numbers.¹⁹ Mir Jalal Khan counts among his descendants. Similarly, some branches have been lost in Balochistan as well. He writes a script, but does not elaborate.²⁰ Muhammad Hayat Khan Buzdar, author of *Tarikh Balochian*, writes that Mir Muhammad Ishaq Khan Bahadur Khan and Mir Ali Nautak were among the four sons of Mir Muhammad. According to him, Ishaq Khan's descendant Ishaqani became famous and this tribe was present in Balochistan for a long time and it goes away. They are spread across the Derajat and throughout the Dera. Even if the same argument is accepted, it is clear that the old genealogy of the Sakhani who are descended from Ishaq Khan is that they are a perverted form of Ishaqani and this tribe is spread throughout the division and their elders Famous people say that he is Ishaqani.²¹ It is in the ancient Ishaqani (Sikh) tradition that our place which is here came from Aleppo on foot and then moved from Dera Ghazi Khan to Taunsa to teach. It is written with reference to K Bo Do Mouth that he came from Kaich Makran. Similarly, it is said about Ghulam Muhammad Sukhani that he came to Dera on foot from Bait Kapahi. And the resident here was the minister of Ghazi Khan VII and when Malik Mukhtiar Khan revolted against Aurangzeb in Sibi area and many campaigns were sent to put an end to this revolt. Malik Mukhtiar Khan who was Prince Mohi-ud-Din Killed by hand and the government within the area of Dhadhar was handed over to Ghazi Khan but he could not

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

handle it for long then it was handed over to Allah Bakhsh Khan who was nephew of Bakhtiar Khan also could not handle it. It is said that this government was given to Islam Khan and Qaim Khan Lodhi but they did not succeed. Rebellions continued here then Prince Mohi-ud-Din then appointed Ghulam Muhammad Khan Sukhani as the governor of this area and with his honors Nawab Also addressed.²²

Similarly, according to Natkani, many people of this tribe were in Bat Kapahi and they took part in the war during the siege of Multan and helped Nawab Muzaffar Khan. There were many who were martyred in it and the names of Mir Ali Khan's sons Mohammad Khan and Mohammad Bakhsh are noteworthy whose graves are in the water of Bat. Abdullah Khan was a man who later on the establishment of British rules. Ghulam Haider Khan Sukhani from Muzaffargarh was the minister of Ghazi Khan VII. This is about before 1770. Ghulam Haider Khan had no children. A large number of people from this nation are also present in education. Among them was Ghulam Muhammad Khan. His sons Abdul Qadir Khan and Abdul Karim Khan made great progress. It was considered a big post. If we look at the past situation, it is clear that there was a very large and well-organized tribe in which many great administrators were born and for a while they ruled over Sibi and Dahadhar and after their It is considered appropriate to go and settle there. Their number is well known in many large areas including Mahryawala, Bait Kapai, Bodo Manha, Parova, Rojhan, Rajanpur, Fazilpur, Samina etc. ²³similarly, in Punjab, it is said that Mazari tribes consider Ishaq as their ancestor despite their separation. And settled here and settled in Kashmore at the end of the fifteenth century. At that time Mazari himself used to live near Koh-i-Bhimber. Sardar Bazan Khan. Once Ishaq Khan came to Bhimber to visit the shrine and it happened again when they met. So Bazan Khan gave him the relationship of his daughter and put Dastarbandi on his head. Some people think that it was Ishaq Khan who came in the fifteenth century and was the leader of Qanuni Baloches here There are also pearls from the record. Thus Mazari came here after a long time and made Rojhan the center and then this area is now running with them. ²⁴

Current Political Role

Similarly, after the formation of Pakistan, however, the Sikhs played a vital role in local politics. In every constituency of Dera Ghazi Khan there is a big vote bank of Sukhani tribe. This plays a decisive role. Sardar Khalid Bilal Khan Sukhani, the then Chief of the Tribe, was elected as the Chief in 2013. He has been elected as the Chairman, Nazim, Member District Corporation. Sardar Muhammad Naeem Khan Sukhani Member District Council was elected several times. Sardar Khalil Ahmad Khan Sukhani was elected Nazim and Chairman. In addition, dozens of people from this tribe have been elected as members, councilors, deputy nazims, and vice chairmen including Muhammad Usman Khalid Sukhani, Munir Ahmad Khan Sukhani, Bilal Khan Sukhani Samina, and Rafiq Khan Sakhani. AD Khan Sukhani Taunsa and Muhammad Ashraf Khan Panjgrahin Taunsa are well known. In the recent local body elections held in KPK, Moazzam Khan has been elected Nazim Prova for the third time. If we consider the central location of this tribe, then at present this tribe is not only in the entire Dera Ghazi Khan division but also in Balochistan, Sindh and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa up to Dera Ismail Khan district. In the plains, especially according to the Baloch population, it is close to the places where abundant water is available. Because like other Baloch tribes, in the beginning the main occupation of the people of this tribe was herding which later shifted to

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

farming. Similarly, the Sikh nation is still present in Sindh, Kashmore in Sindh, then Rojhan, Rajanpur, Fazilpur, Sakhaniwala, Mehrywala Basti Fauja, Jampur, Kotla Sakhani, Dera Ghazi Khan, Samina, Khakhi Gharbi, Sharqi, Rekra. Hazara, Pir Adil, Sadruddin, Marhata, Kala, Shadan Lund, Nautak Sukhani, Masoo Sukhani, Taunsa, Tub, Panjgrahin, Alipur, Head Bakaini, Jatoi, Muzaffargarh, Shahr Sultan, Sanawan, Kot Addu, Jhanjharwali, Dera Ismail Parwa in Khan, Barkhan in Balochistan, Loralai, Sibi, Quetta and many other areas. The recent Sikh National Unity Movement has awakened them because of their philosophy of mutual survival with the vote bank based on electoral democratic principles.

And this has led to an increase in their political representation at the local level. Due to this alliance, they competed in different Union Councils and participated in the elections. Due to which they easily won the elections in many Union Councils in the local body elections. This includes Chairman, Vice Chairman, Councilors. Among those elected are Khalid Bilal Sukhani, the present Chief of the Sikh Nation, Nazir Ahmad Sukhani, Deputy Professor (R) of Alipur, Sardar Moazzam Khan Sukhani, Chairman Union Council Parova, Bilal Khan Sukhani, Chairman, Khalil Ahmad Khan Sukhani, Usman Khalid, Ashiq Khan Sukhani. , And other leaders including Azhar Abbas Khan from Kot Addu, Yaqub Khan Sukhani, Sardar Asif Khan Sukhani from Taunsa, Dr. Abdul Hafeez Khan from Alipur, Sardar Asif Khan from Jampur, Sardar Yusuf Khan from Taunsa, Sardar Khalid Khan Advocate from Supreme Court, Sohail Sardar Sukhani from Taunsa, Hameedullah Khan from Tub, Kaleem Khan from Panjgrahi are trying their best to identify and represent this nation. Similarly in the social field also many people of this nation have served as teachers, lawyers, journalists, doctors over professors and district heads of education department. In addition, Dr. Khalil Ahmad Khan has a full role in DG Health, Divisional Director Statistics, Deputy Director NADRA, and MS District Hospitals and Tehsil Hospitals. Ghulam Muhammad Sukhani Advocate High Court is one of the founding members of Dera Bar. While Khalid Khan Sukhani has the honor of being a lawyer from Taunsa Bar as advocate of Supreme Court. Prof. Nazir Ahmad Khan, whose native area is Pir Adil, has the honor of performing valuable services as Principal in Rajanpur College. Similarly, Prof. Nazir Ahmad Khan Sakhani of Rajanpur also served as Principal, Prof. Musa Kaleem and Prof. Ahmad Khan Sakhani has honor of serving as professors at Gomal University Dera Ismaeel Khan.

Sakhani Welfare Association

Unlike in the past, the powerful Sukhani tribe was completely dispersed in the present and the roots of hypocrisy continued to grow instead of coincidence. There is no such thing as a community. Under these circumstances, some sympathetic hearts of the nation took up the task of uniting him and after a long time made Sardar Tahir Khan Sukhani rich and placed Dastar on his head. Sardar Tahir Khan was the son of famous national hockey player Lala Barbat Tunsui Sukhani. He made every effort to unite the nation. His sudden demise was a blow to the unity of the Sikhs. After the demise of Tahir Khan Sukhani, in 2013, the Sukhani tribe nominated Sardar Khalid Bilal Khan Sukhani as the new chief of the tribe in a large national gathering for the new Amir.

The gathering also proposed a platform to help the deserving and needy people of the nation with mutual unity and solidarity and it was named as Sukhani Welfare Association. Under this, patient support and student support were made mandatory. The platform provided

Historical and Political Role of Sakhani Tribe in the Politics of D.G.Khan

treatment for many patients as well as education for many poor children. Its Marhata branch did its best to provide self-help rations to hundreds of needy people who were unable to meet their needs, especially in the days of Corona, when the lockdown was severe and difficult. This was a unique work of its kind in the countryside which was carried out in the spirit of nationalism.

Conclusion

The above title is the first attempt at an analytical study of the Sukhani tribe. Sukhani is a corrupt new name for the ancient Ishaqani tribe. There was a powerful tribe of the past. Most historians believe that the Sukhani tribe came from Aleppo and came with Mir Chakar when the Baloch arrived in Punjab. But the old Sikh elders think that our ancestors moved from Aleppo to Kerman and then from Kerman to Makran and from Makran to Dera Ghazi Khan. Even today it is in the old record. The Balochi-inhabited region today adopts the Saraiki language and is said to be a part of this culture. In short, it was a powerful tribe, but that is no longer the case. However, it still holds a key position in regional politics.

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